

STUDY ON THE EFFECT OF STACKING SEQUENCE ON TENSILE, FLEXURAL AND IMPACT BEHAVIOR IN CARBON/BASALT/GLASS/KEVLAR EPOXY HYBRID POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: Composite materials play a significant role in modern aircraft, missiles, submarines and sports equipment due to their exceptional strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios, as well as their superior durability, fatigue resistance and corrosion resistance. This study examined the mechanical properties, specifically the tensile, flexural, and impact strengths, of hybrid laminated polymer composites. This study focuses on how hybridization and stacking sequences affect these properties. Specifically, eight-layered composites were fabricated using plain-woven basalt (B), carbon (C), Kevlar (K), and glass (G) fibers as reinforcements with epoxy resin (LY556). The laminates, featuring symmetric stacking sequences, were produced via hot press molding at 2 MPa and 100°C. Mechanical testing was conducted using an instrumented universal testing machine to determine the tensile and flexural properties, while a Charpy impact tester was used to assess the impact resistance. The findings indicate that the stacking sequence of the layers is pivotal in influencing the tensile, flexural, and impact properties of the composite. The findings have significant practical implications in industries such as aerospace, automotive and sports equipment manufacturing, where the enhancement of material properties is crucial for optimizing both performance and safety.

KEYWORDS: Polymer Composites, Hybridization, Stacking sequence, Strength

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, hybrid fiber-reinforced polymer composites have garnered significant attention owing to their ability to blend the beneficial properties of various fiber types while addressing the limitations of individual fibers. The arrangement of different fiber layers is crucial in determining the overall mechanical performance of these composites, influencing tensile strength, flexural properties, and impact resistance. Carbon, basalt, glass, and Kevlar fibers impart distinct characteristics to hybrid composites, making their strategic arrangement vital for optimizing their mechanical properties [1,2].

1.1 Effects of Stacking Sequence on Tensile Properties

Recent research has shown that the arrangement of layers significantly affects the tensile properties of hybrid composites. The addition of surface intraply carbon-Kevlar layers to basalt-reinforced epoxy composites resulted in a 27.40% improvement in

tensile strength compared to composites made solely of basalt. The tensile strength rose from 332.41 MPa in pure basalt composites to 423.52 MPa in hybrid composites, underscoring the beneficial effects of hybridization [1]. Studies on hybrid composites made of carbon and glass fibers have shown that the arrangement of layers is the primary factor influencing the flexural modulus, whereas the hybrid ratio has a negligible effect. In interlayer hybrid composites, placing carbon fibers on the top or bottom surfaces results in the highest flexural modulus, particularly when the carbon fiber content is balanced with other fibers [3]. A detailed investigation of hybrid natural fiber composites revealed that the order in which the layers are arranged significantly affects the tensile strength. The composites with alternating layers displayed varied performance traits. The research indicated that grouping layers of the same material type together generally enhanced tensile strength by minimizing

interfacial layers and boosting interfacial adhesion [2].

1.2 Flexural Properties and Stacking Configuration

The flexural characteristics of hybrid composites are highly influenced by changes in the stacking sequence. In carbon-basalt hybrid systems, alternating the fiber orientations between 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ results in enhanced flexural performance. Among the configurations tested, the S-9 arrangement with a stacking sequence of $0^\circ/45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/45^\circ/0^\circ$ exhibited the highest ultimate flexural strength [4]. For carbon-glass hybrid composites, the flexural strength and modulus were strongly dependent on the sequence of the fiber reinforcement. When the carbon layers were positioned at the exterior surfaces, the maximum flexural modulus could be achieved, essentially matching the performance of pure carbon composites. Conversely, placing glass layers at exterior positions resulted in lower flexural modulus but improved failure strain characteristics [5-6]. Research on basalt-carbon hybrid composites has revealed that hybrid sequences, such as [C₄B₄], exhibit more gradual degradation, characterized by significant matrix cracking and fiber pull-out, thereby demonstrating superior energy absorption capabilities compared to configurations composed solely of carbon. The enhanced toughness and relatively lower stiffness of basalt fibers contribute to increased energy absorption during flexural loading [7].

1.3 Impact Behavior and Energy Absorption

The impact characteristics of hybrid composites are significantly affected by the fiber type and stacking order. The inclusion of Carbon-Kevlar intraply surface layers increased the impact strength by 24.4% compared to composites made solely of basalt, achieving a value of 136.25 kJ/m². This enhancement is credited to the improved toughness and energy absorption capabilities offered by the hybrid design [1]. Studies on thermoplastic carbon fiber/aluminum hybrid composites have shown that fiber-metal laminates possess a higher specific energy absorption capacity than pure carbon fiber composites. The specific energy absorption of these hybrid laminates exceeds that of pure carbon composites by 3.7%, and the energy absorption per unit thickness has increased by 24.4% [8]. Studies on hybrid composites integrating basalt and carbon fibers have identified delamination at the fiber-matrix interface and fiber pull-out as the predominant failure modes during impact. Different stacking sequences have been shown to possess unique energy absorption properties, with basalt-rich configurations exhibiting more ductile failure

behaviors compared to those primarily composed of carbon [7].

1.4 Interlaminar Shear Strength Considerations

Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) is a vital factor in the effectiveness of hybrid composites and is significantly affected by the order in which the layers are arranged. Research on hybrid systems combining carbon, glass, and Kevlar fibers has shown that the highest ILSS values are obtained in setups that include carbon and glass fibers. In contrast, configurations featuring Kevlar fibers exhibit the lowest ILSS values, due to the weaker bond between the fiber and the matrix.[9]. The arrangement of various fiber types within a laminate structure influence both its flexural and interlaminar shear strength. Research has shown that the fiber content and arrangement in the laminate impact these properties, indicating a possible interconnection. To achieve optimal performance, high-modulus fibers should be strategically placed to enhance load transfer efficiency [9].

1.5 Optimization Strategies and Design Guidelines

Recent studies have identified several design principles for optimizing stacking sequences in hybrid composites. For applications involving tension, fibers with a higher specific strength should be placed in the outer layers, whereas those with a lower strength are more suitable for the inner layers. This arrangement enhances the overall strength of the composite by maximizing the contribution of high-performance fibers [10]. In scenarios where bending is involved, optimal results are achieved by positioning the carbon fibers on the side experiencing tension and the glass fibers on the side facing compression. This arrangement takes advantage of the exceptional tensile strength of the carbon fibers while also utilizing the superior compressive characteristics of the glass fibers. Similarly, when Kevlar fibers are employed, they should be placed on the tension side to maximize the composite's overall effectiveness [3],[9]. Utilizing advanced optimization techniques such as Taguchi methods and Grey Relational Analysis, researchers have determined the best combinations of fiber volume fractions, particle sizes, and curing parameters. These methods have resulted in a 15-20% improvement in tensile strength and a 22% boost in impact resistance when the optimal settings are applied [11,12,13].

1.6 Failure Mechanisms and Morphological Analysis

Microscopic examination revealed unique failure patterns that depended on the stacking sequence.

Configurations composed entirely of carbon exhibit brittle fractures, characterized by sudden matrix failure and minimal delamination owing to their high rigidity. Conversely, hybrid configurations that include basalt or glass fibers show a more gradual failure process involving fiber pullout, matrix deformation, and fiber bridging. SEM analysis suggested that the hybrid specimens had enhanced toughness and energy absorption capabilities compared to pure-fiber composites, which explains the superior impact performance of a well-designed hybridization[1],[7].

1.7 Recent Developments and Future Directions

Recent research has investigated the combination of nanoparticles with hybrid fiber systems. Incorporating nanopolypropylene into carbon-basalt hybrids achieved peak performance at a concentration of 6 wt. %, with CBCBC stacking sequences surpassing BCBCB configurations [12]. Thermoplastic-based hybrid composites, particularly those incorporating polyether ether ketone (PEEK) in fiber-metal laminates, exhibit promising impact resistance. However, further study is needed to determine the best stacking sequences for high-velocity impact response[8]. Overall stacking sequence significantly influences mechanical properties of carbon/basalt/glass/Kevlar epoxy hybrid composites. Surface placement of high-modulus fibers enhances tensile strength by 27%; layer structure is more critical than hybrid ratio for flexural properties; hybrid configurations achieve 24% impact strength improvements; and fiber-specific positioning strategies optimize performance for specific loading conditions.

2 FABRICATION OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES AND TESTING

Hybrid fiber-reinforced polymer composite laminates were fabricated with eight layers in symmetric configurations. The symmetric configuration was selected because it prevents the laminate from twisting owing to thermal loads, such as cooling from the processing temperature. Plain-woven basalt fiber (400GSM), plain-woven carbon fiber (400GSM), plain-woven Kevlar fiber (400GSM), and plain-woven glass fibers (400GSM) were used as the reinforcement layers. The fibers were obtained from Composites Tomorrow (Vadodara, Gujarat, India). An epoxy resin (Araldite LY 556) and hardener (HY 917) were used to fabricate the hybrid composite laminates. They were purchased from Herenba Instruments and Engineers, Ambattur, Chennai. The hybrid composite laminates were fabricated at Polymer India Pvt. Ltd., Bommasandara Industrial Area, Bangalore, India. In

the fabrication process, the fibers were first cut into dimensions of 300 × 300 mm, and laminated fabrics were manufactured by applying epoxy resin to the fiber layers, layer by layer, according to the desired stacking sequence. The stacking sequences and fiber configurations of the laminated fabrics are listed in Table 1 and Fig.1.

Table 1. Layup sequence of laminated fabrics.

Material Name	Fabric used	Lay-up Sequence
A	Hybrid (Kevlar/Basalt/Glass/Carbon/Epoxy)	$[(0^{\circ}K/0^{\circ}B/0^{\circ}G/0^{\circ}C)_2]_s$
B	Hybrid (Carbon/Kevlar/Glass/Basalt/Epoxy)	$[(0^{\circ}C/0^{\circ}K/0^{\circ}G/0^{\circ}B)_2]_s$
C	Hybrid (Kevlar/Basalt/Carbon/Glass/Epoxy)	$[(0^{\circ}K/0^{\circ}B/0^{\circ}C/0^{\circ}G)_2]_s$
D	Hybrid (Carbon/Basalt/Glass/Kevlar/Epoxy)	$[(0^{\circ}C/0^{\circ}B/0^{\circ}G/0^{\circ}K)_2]_s$

Stacking sequence 1 (KBGCCGBK) is called A stacking sequence 2 (CKGBBGKC) is called B stacking sequence 3 (KBCGGCBK) is called C and the last stacking sequence 4 (CBGKKGBC) is called D.

Fig.1 Stacking sequence diagram

Fig.2 Compression molding unit and the mold

A mold of 300 × 300 mm was prepared, and release gel was applied, followed by heating until the required temperature was reached. The fiber fabrics were cut into 300 × 300 mm shapes and kept ready for use. The resin and hardener were mixed in a ratio of 10:1. The mold was removed, resin was applied to the mold, and laminated fabrics were laid on a flat mold and subjected to 2 MPa pressure for 1 h curing

time at 100°C temperature. The fabricated hybrid composite laminates were then cooled to room temperature under pressure (Fig.2). The final composite lamina with dimensions of 300 mm × 300 mm is shown in Fig. 2. In the fabricated composite laminates, the average thickness of all the hybrid composite laminates was 10 mm (+/- 0.5 mm).

2.2 Fabrication Method

- Cutting of fabrics and hybridization
- Laminated fabrics preparation
- Application of resin mixture
- Molding with hot press
- Curing of fabricated laminates

2.3 Cutting of Specimen

The required test specimens (tensile, flexural, impact, and vibration) were cut to the desired dimensions from the composite plates using water-jet machining at M/s. Om Water Jet Machining Pvt. Ltd., Bangalore. The dimensions of the test specimens were determined according to the ASTM standards.

- The tensile test specimen dimensions were determined according to ASTM D638-14.
- The impact test specimen dimensions were determined according to ASTM D256-04.
- The dimensions of the flexural test specimens were determined according to ASTM D7264

2.4. Mechanical Characterization

To characterize the mechanical behavior of the hybrid fiber-reinforced polymer composites, the following mechanical tests were performed on the cut specimens:

- Tensile test
- Flexural test
- Impact test

2.5. Tensile Testing

Tensile tests were performed using a bench-mounted universal testing machine (Lloyd Material Testing, EZ 20) with a 20 kN load cell. Tensile testing was conducted at ARML Pvt. Ltd., Electronics City, Bengaluru, India. The specimens were prepared according to ASTM D638 – 14 standard. The gauge length of the tensile test specimen was 25 mm. The tensile specimens were loaded under tension at a constant crosshead speed of 5 mm/min. Two samples were tested for each composite laminate type. A load versus displacement curve was obtained for all

measurements. Fig.3 shows the test setup used for tensile testing.

Fig.3 Tensile test setup

2.6. Flexural Testing

Flexural tests (3-point bending test) were carried out on a fully automated universal testing machine, which was aided by Kalpak software according to ASTM D 7264. A 10 kN load cell was used, and load versus deflection curves were collected for all measurements. The flexural strengths were then calculated using the load versus deflection curves. Two samples (dimensions: 200 × 20 mm; span length: 140 mm) were tested for each type of composite. Fig.4 shows the dimensions along with the points of loading of the flexural test specimen.

Fig.4 Specimen under flexural test

2.8 Impact Testing

Charpy impact tests on notched specimens were performed following ASTM D256 using an impact tester and a hammer of 25J. The specimens were notched using water jet cutting. The test equipment used for the Charpy impact test is shown in Fig.5. Two specimens were tested for each type of composite, and the impact energies absorbed were recorded.

Fig.5 Impact test setup

2.9 Density Test

The density of each specimen was tested using Archimede’s principle. The measured density values are shown in the Table 2 and Fig.6.

Table 2. Density of different stacking sequences

Material	Density (Kg/m ³)
A	1291.9
B	1254.2
C	1281.8
D	1304

Fig.6 Density variation for different materials

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tensile Test Results

The tensile properties of the hybrid polymer composite laminates were tested. Stress-strain curves were then plotted for the hybrid composite laminates as shown in Fig.7. From the load versus displacement curve, it is clear that Material B will take more load than the other materials. The Young's modulus of the individual samples was determined by analyzing the slope of the stress-strain graph. Tensile strength and Young’s modulus is listed in the Table 3 and Table 4 respectively. The bar graph illustrates the variation in Young’s modulus for the four materials in which Material B with carbon fiber as outer layer exhibited the highest value.

Table 3. Tensile strength of different sequences

Material	Stacking sequence	Tensile strength (MPa)
A	KBGCCGBK	155
B	CKGBBGKC	219
C	KBCGGCBK	140
D	CBGKKGBC	124

Fig.7: Stress -strain curves

Fig. 8 Tensile strength of different materials

Table 4: Young’s modulus for different stacking sequences

Material	Young’s modulus (GPa)
A	2.45
B	3.21
C	1.52
D	1.31

Fig. 9: Young’s modulus for different stacking sequences graph

The tensile strength of the hybrid composite depends on its stacking sequence, density, and temperature. As the temperature did not vary during testing, it did not affect the results. The analysis of the results and the stress-strain graph indicate that Materials A and C exhibit nearly identical tensile strengths, attributable to the application of Kevlar as the surface material. In samples A and C, no significant effect of the stacking sequence was observed, as only the inner layer was interchanged in these materials. It is also observed that the density of both materials is almost equal, which explains why the strength of both materials is nearly the same.

Fig.10: Broken samples of tensile test

The reduced strength of Material D can be attributed to the incorporation of less elastic materials, such as Kevlar and glass, as the innermost layers. Examination of the fractured samples indicates that the inner layers were the initial points of rupture, ultimately resulting in the complete failure of the sample. Material B, with the highest strength of 219 MPa, is 28.9%, 43.12%, and 37.78% stronger than Materials A, C, and D, respectively. The use of carbon as the outermost layer and basalt in the inner layer contributed to good bonding. The Young’s modulus of Material B is higher than the other three, indicating that this stacking sequence produced the best result in the tensile test.

3.2 Flexural Test Results

The flexural properties of hybrid composite laminates were evaluated through testing. Load-deflection curves were generated for these composite laminates. Based on the obtained load-deflection curves, the bending strength was determined. Table 5 presents the results on bending strength.

Fig. 11 Load versus displacement in bending test

Table 5: Bending strength of different stacking sequences

Material	Maximum load (kN)	Bending strength (MPa)
A	2.35	305
B	1.37	146
C	2.4	301
D	2.38	305

Fig. 12 Bar graph showing bending test results for different test specimens

Fig.13: Broken samples of bending test

The data presented in the Fig.12 indicates that Materials A, C, and D exhibit comparable bending strength, suggesting that the stacking sequence exerts minimal influence on this property. Material B, which demonstrates the lowest bending strength at 146 MPa, reveals that despite the higher elastic properties of the inner and outer layers, the middle layers, composed of glass and basalt, possess lower elastic properties. This discrepancy results in the rupture of the intermediate layer. It is also noted that the material did not experience complete rupture as shown in Fig.13. The application of materials with higher elastic properties on the surface and core contributes to an increase in bending strength.

3.3 Impact Test Results

The hybrid composite laminates underwent testing to evaluate their impact properties. The absorbed impact energies were documented and the Charpy impact strengths were subsequently calculated. The Charpy impact strengths for the various hybrid composite laminates are presented in Fig.14.

Fig. 14 Bar graph for impact strength

Fig.15 Broken samples of impact test

Materials A, C, and D exhibit comparable impact strength, suggesting that the stacking sequence does not significantly influence this property. Additionally, it was noted that Materials A and D did not undergo complete fracture. Material B, possessing the highest impact strength of 140 KJ/m², demonstrates superior performance attributed to the incorporation of highly elastic materials in both the surface and core layers. The impact energy absorbed by Material B exceeds that of Materials A, C, and D by 28.1%, 35.89%, and 44%, respectively. This indicates that employing high-density materials as the inner and outer layers enhances the overall impact strength. Fig.15 illustrates the fracture patterns of the materials.

4 CONCLUSION

Through comprehensive mechanical testing of hybrid polymer composite laminates, several significant findings have emerged, underscoring the importance of optimizing stacking sequences to achieve desired mechanical properties. The experimental results indicated that composite configuration B exhibited superior tensile strength compared to all other tested variants, thereby establishing the positioning of carbon fiber on the surface as optimal for tensile applications. The hybridization strategy, which incorporates carbon as the surface material with Kevlar and basalt as intermediate layers, effectively enhanced tensile performance. However, the placement of less elastic materials in the inner layers led to a failure cascade, where the rupture of inner layers preceded the failure of outer layers, resulting in a reduction of overall tensile strength for material D. The three-point bending tests revealed that materials A, C and D displayed similar flexural performance, suggesting that the stacking sequence had a limited impact on the flexural properties of these configurations. In contrast, material B exhibited reduced flexural strength and incomplete rupture patterns, which were attributed to the premature failure of the inner glass and basalt layers. This finding diverges from research indicating that positioning carbon fibers on the top and bottom surfaces maximizes flexural

strength in hybrid composites. Charpy impact testing indicated that material B exhibited the highest impact strength, measuring 140 kJ/m², whereas materials A, C, and D displayed comparable impact resistance values. The superior impact performance of material B is attributed to the presence of high elastic modulus carbon fibers at both the surface and innermost positions, which enhance its energy absorption capabilities. This study confirms that the stacking sequence exerts a significant influence on the mechanical properties under various loading conditions. Positioning carbon fibers as outer layers optimizes tensile strength, while alternative arrangements enhance impact resistance, thereby validating that strategic stacking control facilitates the tailoring of properties for specific applications. All tested hybrid composite configurations satisfy aircraft structural requirements, demonstrating essential strength, stiffness, and impact resistance suitable for aerospace applications. The validated configurations exhibit direct applicability in aerospace structural components, including control surfaces and fairings. Future research should concentrate on multi-scale modeling incorporating machine learning optimization, long-term fatigue behaviour under complex loading, automated manufacturing processes for hybrid production and sustainable recycling methodologies for multi-fibre systems. The investigation of multifunctional hybrid composites with the integration of smart materials represents promising research frontiers.

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